

Agro2Circular

D8.10 – Contribution to standardization (FINAL)

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1. List of abbreviations

CEN European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC European Committee for electrotechnical Standardization
CWA Workshop Agreements
ETSI European Telecommunications Standards Institute
IEC International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO International standardization organization
SC Subcommittee
TC Technical committee
TS Technical Specifications
TR Technical Reports
WG Working group

2. Executive summary <abstract>

The main objective of the standardization activities in Agro2Circular is to facilitate the market acceptance of the results by exploiting these results and findings to develop new standards that have a wide market recognition. The standardization process is considered very valuable for the market uptake of the A2C results and for the impact of the project beyond the financing period.

This deliverable summarized the standardization actions carried out by the A2C consortium, guided by UNE (Spanish Association for Standardization) acting as member of ISO (International Standardization Organization) and of CEN (European Committee for Standardization), among other international standardization organizations.

The A2C standardization strategy that was defined in the first part of the project is reported and explained.

The deliverable describes the interaction of the A2C consortium with the selected standardization technical committees (TC), that were pre-identified as relevant for the A2C project, mainly the CEN/TC 249 – Plastics and CEN/TC 261/SC 4 - Degradability and organic recycling of packaging and packaging material. Also, it describes the A2C contribution to the development, drafting and revision of different standards in specific CEN working groups within the aforementioned TCs.

This document also describes the process for the agreement of a standard CWA (CEN Workshop Agreements), proposed and led by A2C, and developed under a CEN Workshop launched ad hoc on 'Guidelines for characterization of extracts for the recycling/upcycling of organic agrifood wastes'. The [CWA 18149:2024](#) was published by CEN in 2024-10-09 and available for free download in the [CEN/CENELEC download area](#).

3. Standardization Strategy

The A2C standardization strategy was elaborated in M12 of the A2C project. The strategy is described in this deliverable and it explains the phases to be addressed by A2C during the project timeframe, and the different possible routes for A2C to explore.

In the following section 4 ‘Implementation’ of this deliverable, the routes that have been finally taken by A2C are explained in detail.

The A2C standardization strategy includes 3 different phases: 1. First contact with standardization technical committees, 2. Subsequent (potential) interactions with standardization committees and 3. Standardization process.

Phases 2 and 3 could overlap in time. In line with the elaborated strategy, the contribution to standardization of Agro2Circular is based on:

1. The feedback received from the interaction with the relevant Standardization Technical Committees
 2. The suitability of the project outcomes to be transferred into new standards by means of the initiation of a standardization process within the standardization organizations.
- The Agro2Circular standardization strategy considers the different actions and routes represented in the figure below:

Figure 1 – Agro2Circular Strategy for the contribution to standardization

The different steps are explained below. Each phase includes different options that are analyzed by the Agro2Circular consortium, to determine the more appropriate actions to be

carried out on the base of the standardization landscape (reported in D8.8 at M6), and also considering available resources and timing within the project.

3.1 First contact with the standardization technical committees

The objective of this first contact is to raise awareness about Agro2Circular among the relevant standardization committees and to ease subsequent contacts. Different categories of stakeholders at European/international level are present in these committees, so the standardization system is used as a targeted dissemination channel. Feedback is requested to gather any view, opinion or advice about the project and the standardization possibilities or needs. Additionally, this first contact is useful to determine the best path towards the initiation of a standardization process, moreover this first step is expected to ease future contacts within the A2C project timeframe.

The A2C execution of the first contacts with TCs is explained in Section 4.1.

3.2 Subsequent interaction with the standardization technical committees

Different relationships can be established with the selected technical committees. Two factors determine the more suitable interactions: 1. the impact/relevance for Agro2Circular of the standardization works within the committees and; 2. the feasibility of initiating a standardization process within a standardization committee (versus initiating the standardization process within a workshop created ad hoc, details are given below). The possible ways of interaction of the A2C project with the TCs to be explored are:

- Follow-up the activity of the relevant standardization committees. This allows to detect the initiation of standardization works that can be relevant for Agro2Circular and the progress of significant existing under-development standards. This is achievable through a periodical monitoring of the standardization activity resulting in updates of the standardization landscape.
- Further contact with the standardization committees to update the progress of Agro2Circular. This is achievable by delivering reports, by attending relevant technical committees' meetings or by joint events. On the one hand, this action contributes to further dissemination of the project and can guide the initiation of the standardization process.
- The participation of one or more Agro2Circular partners in the standardization technical committees. Standardization is an open activity and all interested parties may participate in the technical committees through the designation of their National Standardization Body. This option allows for a deeper follow-up of the activity of a

standardization committee and it is valuable if the standardization process is going to be initiated within the standardization committee.

- The establishment of a formal liaison of Agro2Circular with the standardization committees. It is recommended only when the work of the standardization committee is closely linked with the main goals of the project and a direct technical contribution from the project is expected.

The interactions with TCs carried out by A2C are described in Section 4.2.

3.3 Standardization process

The main objective of the standardization activities in Agro2Circular is to facilitate the market acceptance of the results by transferring these results and findings to standards that have a wide recognition in the market. With the collaboration of the relevant partners, the feasible results to go through a standardization process are identified. Different options to contribute to standardization are considered depending on the kind of the results (nature, availability and intellectual property rights) and the standardization context (existence of closely related standards and reactions of the standardization committees).

The **different options explored by A2C to contribute to standardization** are:

- Development of a new standard within a standardization workshop. A standardization workshop is a group of entities with a common interest in developing a standard about a specific issue. It is the equivalent figure to the standardization committee, but the number of participants is typically smaller and the working procedures are faster and more flexible. A standardization workshop is created when there is a need of developing a precise standard in an innovative field that is not covered by the existing standardization committees or when the standard does not fit into the committees' work program. If the subject is close to the field covered by a standardization committee, it shall be informed and it shall allow to launch the standardization workshop.

In the European environment, the standardization workshop is named CEN-CENELEC Workshop and the corresponding developed standard is called CEN-CENELEC Workshop Agreement (CWA). The nature and timeline for the development of CWAs is very suitable for R&I projects.

- Standardization within a standardization committee. To standardize the Agro2Circular results within a standardization committee may be interesting or needed. The possible scenarios are:
 - a. New standard development within a standardization committee. This option applies to a new standard whose scope is covered by an existing

standardization committee, which decides to include it in its work program. The resulting standard have the support of the standardization committee, but the work shall be adapted to the internal timeline of such standardization committee and could go beyond the timeframe of the project.

- b. Contribute to an on-going standard. As a consequence of the monitoring of the standardization landscape, it may be found that the Agro2Circular results are covered by a standard under development but that these results do not fit in the current standard draft. Gaps in standards may be found in both: 1- standards that are being developed from a new initiative and 2- standards already published that are going under a review process towards a new version.
- c. Request the modification of a standard that is not under development or review. The gap may be found also in published standards that are not under any work within the standardization committee. In this case, a fully justified modification request can be made to the standardization committee.
- d. Outline of a future standard. Only when there is not a clear view on a full roadmap for the contribution to standardization (like lack of agreement within the Consortium or lack of the expected results).

The routes taken by A2C to contribute to standardization are described in Section 4.3.

4. Implementation

The actions and approaches that have been performed for the implementation of each step of the strategy are detailed below.

4.1 First contact with the standardization technical committees

For the “first contact” implementation, the relevant standardization committees to contact were selected among those that were identified in the standardization landscape related to the Agro2Circular project (D8.8).

The selection was performed on the basis of possible standardizable outcomes from A2C. The standardizable innovative outcomes were identified mainly in the following areas:

- General waste and biowaste
- Plastics: plastics recycling, environmental aspects, bio-based and biodegradable plastics, and thermoplastic films for use in agriculture.

Regarding the rest of technical areas identified in D8.8 (“Circular economy”, “LCA”, “Food, Cosmetics, Extracts”, “Biotechnology” and “Information technology”), in principle standardizable A2C outcomes are not foreseen, or the scopes of the corresponding TCs do not match with the possible A2C outcomes (the consideration of these other TCs and the corresponding selected standards has been taken into account to guarantee compliance and compatibility with established requirements and technologies, and as information source for the A2C R&D developments).

Accordingly, the standardization committees proposed for contacting with, for the objectives described in 3.1., are indicated in the following Table:

Technical area	Standardization Technical Committees
General waste and biowaste	CEN/TC 444 Environmental characterization of solid matrices
Plastics	CEN/TC 249 Plastics: CEN/TC 249/WG 7 Thermoplastic films for use in agriculture CEN/TC 249/WG 9 Characterization of degradability CEN/TC 249/WG 11 Plastics/Plastics recycling

Table 1 – Identification of standardization committees to be contacted

The information to disseminate to the TCs avoiding any confidential content was agreed between the A2C coordinator and the partner UNE (Spanish Association for

Standardization). A dossier was elaborated for sharing with the selected CEN/TCs (Annex 1)

The following information was shared by email with the secretary of the CEN/TC 444 in March 2023.

Dear XXXX

I'm addressing you on behalf of the H2020 project Agro2Circular which aim is *A2C is to boost the upcycling of agri-food wastes (from fruit and vegetables, and multilayer plastic films) through innovative routes of valorisation, leading to high extraction yields, bioactives with the purity and stability required to be used for the production of new food, cosmetic and nutraceutical formulation.*

As part of this project, under the responsibility of UNE (Spanish standardization body) representing CEN/CENELEC in Agro2Circular, specific standardization activities are included to:

- Ensure compatibility with existing technologies by the identification of relevant existing standards.
- Maximize dissemination to proper stakeholders by addressing the relevant standardization technical committees.
- Contribute with the findings and knowledge generated during the project to the development of standardization in the field.

The link with CEN/TC 444 comes from the objective of the Project of improving the upcycling of agri-food wastes that pass also through the better characterization of the wastes considering their final destination and applications. Standards from CEN/TC 444 dealing with characterization of waste and biowaste were identified as relevant for the project.

For your information, other CEN and ISO TCs will also be contacted with this information.

The objective of this contact is, on the one hand, to raise awareness on the project to these TCs and gather feedback on any suggestion, question or comment. On the other hand, it is intended in the second half of the project the Agro2Circular contribution to standardization from the selected/standardizable project results. Depending on several factors such as the nature of these results and the standardization landscape at the corresponding moment, this contribution to standardization may be oriented to generate new pre-standards (Workshop Agreements) or to participate at TC level.

Please, find attached a brief summary containing more information about Agro2Circular and also the webpage here: <https://agro2circular.eu/>. Feel free to circulate this information to your TC members or to anyone you consider potentially interested in the objectives and results of the project. Now the project is nearly 1/2 progressed and we would be very grateful if you could give us feedback regarding the interest of this project for the activity of the TC. Additionally, any suggestion, question or comment related to the project would be very useful.

If you find that additional information would be welcome, as well as other kinds of contact (a dedicated telco, attending a TC, SC or WG meeting to explain the project, etc.) we would be pleased to address it.

Thank you in advance for your attention and looking forward to your reply.

Best regards,

Project manager R&I
Spanish Association for Standardization – UNE

The following information was shared by email with the secretary of the CEN/TC 249 in March 2023.

Dear XXXX

I'm addressing you on behalf of the H2020 project Agro2Circular which aim is *to boost the upcycling of agri-food wastes (from fruit and vegetables, and multilayer plastic films) through innovative routes of valorisation, leading to high extraction yields, bioactives with the purity and stability required to be used for the production of new food, cosmetic and nutraceutical formulation.*

As part of this project, under the responsibility of UNE (Spanish standardization body) representing CEN/CENELEC in Agro2Circular, specific standardization activities are included to:

- Ensure compatibility with existing technologies by the identification of relevant existing standards.
- Maximize dissemination to proper stakeholders by addressing the relevant standardization technical committees and
- Contribute with the findings and knowledge generated during the project to the development of standardization in the field.

CEN/TC 249 is closely related to the Agro2Circular scope, and indeed many of the standards of this TC were identified as very relevant for the project, including standards related to plastics recycling, environmental aspects, bio-based and biodegradable plastics, and thermoplastic films for use in agriculture.

Also for your information, other CEN TCs will be also contacted with this information.

The objective of this contact is, on the one hand, to raise awareness on the project to this TCs and gather feedback on any suggestion, question or comment. On the other hand, it is intended in the second half of the project the Agro2Circular contribution to standardization from the selected/standardizable project results. Depending on several factors such as the nature of these results and the standardization landscape at the corresponding moment, this contribution to standardization may be oriented to generate new pre-standards (Workshop Agreements).

At this moment, Agro2Circular experts are already participating or managing to join different WG (WG 7, 9 and 11), related also to the on-going EC standardization request.

Please, find attached a brief summary containing more information about Agro2Circular and also the webpage here: <https://agro2circular.eu/>. Feel free to circulate this information to your TC members or to anyone you consider potentially interested in the objectives and results of the project. Now the project is nearly 1/2 progressed and any suggestion, question or comment related with the project would be very useful.

If you find that additional information would be welcome, as well as other kind of contact (a dedicated telco, attending a TC, SC or WG meeting to explain the project, etc.) we would be pleased to address it.

Thank you in advance for your attention and looking forward to your reply.
Best regards,

Project manager R&D
Spanish Association for Standardization – UNE

4.2 Subsequent interaction with the standardization technical committees

In the Agro2Circular standardization landscape (D. 8.8), active standard developments were identified in several fields, mainly related to plastics in agriculture and plastic recycling. The A2C involvement in these developments was considered very relevant to ensure that the new standards are including the A2C solutions and do not constitute a barrier for their exploitation.

Furthermore, as a result of the continuous A2C standardization activity monitoring, it was identify a new EC request to CEN/CENELEC for the development of new standards regarding plastics recycling and recycled plastics in support of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy.

To address the A2C implication in the aforementioned works, different interactions have been carried out between Agro2Circular and specific European standardization working groups, within the CEN/TC 249 – *Plastics* and CEN/TC 261/SC 4 - *Degradability and organic recycling of packaging and packaging material*. The resulting A2C contributions from these interactions are described below on the section 4.3.1.

4.3 Standardization process

The different possible routes for the Agro2Circular contribution to standardization were analyzed within subsequent A2C General Assemblies (see section 3.3 for the possible routes).

Three different routes were identified as the more suitable ones:

- Contribution to on-going standards within existing CEN Technical Committees.
- Development of a new pre-standard via CEN workshop: publication of CEN Workshop Agreement CWA.

4.3.1 Contribution to on-going standards within existing Technical Committees

Through the participation of the partners CETEC and SOLPLAST in specific working groups, A2C has contributed to the development, drafting and revision of different standards, as explained below:

- CEN/TC 249/WG 7 - *Thermoplastic films for use in agriculture*. Participation of the partner SOLPLAST in different meeting, dealing with the needs for revision of standards about agricultural films with the aim to include the use of recycled products in these materials. Through the participation of the partner SOLPLAST, Agro2Circular were represented during the revision of the following standards:
 - EN 13206 Plastics - Thermoplastic covering films for use in agriculture and horticulture
 - EN 13207 Plastics - Thermoplastic silage films and tubes for use in agriculture
 - EN 13655 Plastics - Thermoplastic mulch films recoverable after use, for use in agriculture and horticulture
 - EN 17033 Plastics - Thermoplastic mulch films recoverable after use, for use in agriculture and horticulture
 - EN 14932 Plastics - Thermoplastic stretch films for wrapping silage bales
 - EN 17098-1 Plastics - Barrier films for agricultural and horticultural soil disinfection by fumigation - Part 1: Specifications for barrier films

SOLPLAST has participated actively in the design and drafting these standards. The revised versions have been already submitted to enquiry by CEN, and their final publication is expected in 2025.

- CEN/TC 249/WG 9 - *Bio-based and biodegradable plastics*. The partner CETEC has participated in the process of study and confirmation of the EN 14995:2006 “*Plastics - Evaluation of compostability - Test scheme and specifications*” for the time being for another five years. In addition CETEC has monitored the standardization activity of the technical report FprCEN/TR 17910 “*Biodegradable plastics - Status of standardization and new prospects*”.
- CEN/TC 249/WG 26 - *Agricultural Plastic products – Design for recycling, use, removal, collection and recycling*. The partner SOLPLAST has participated actively in the development of the standard draft prEN 18109 (WI=00249A5I) “*Plastics - Agricultural plastic products - Installation, use, removal, sorting, collection, preparation for recycling and design for recycling guidelines*”. The final draft was ready to be submitted to formal vote for publication.

- CEN/TC 249/WG 11 - *Plastics recycling*. Participation of the partners CETEC and SOLPLAST monitoring the standardization activity regarding the following standardization documents:
 - FprCEN/TS 17627 Plastics - Recycled plastics - Determination of solid contaminants content
 - FprEN 18064-6 Plastics — Quality recommendations and basis for specifications for application of plastic recyclates in products — Part 6: Polystyrene (PS)
 - FprEN 18064-5 Plastics - Quality recommendations and basis for specifications for application of plastic recyclates in products - Part 5: Poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC)
 - FprEN 18064-4 Quality recommendations and basis for specifications for application of plastic recyclates in products - Part 4 : Poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET)
 - FprEN 18064-3 Plastics Quality recommendations and basis for specifications for application of plastic recyclates in products - Part 3 : Polypropylene (PP)
 - FprEN 18064-2 Plastics - Quality recommendations and basis for specifications for application of plastic recyclates in products - Part 2: Polyethylene (PE)
 - FprEN 18064-1 Thermoplastic elastomers - Nomenclature and abbreviated terms
 - prEN 18065 Plastics - Recycled plastics - Classification of recycled plastics based on Data Quality Levels for use and (digital) trading
 - prCWA "Plastics - Recycled plastics -Characterization of polyvinyl butyral (PVB) recyclates"
 - prEN 15347-6 Quality grades of sorted polystyrene (PS) wastes and specific test methods
 - prEN 15347-5 Quality grades of sorted poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC) wastes and specific test methods
 - prEN 15347-4 Quality grades of sorted poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) wastes and specific test methods
 - prEN 15347-3 Quality grades of sorted Polypropylene (PP) wastes and specific test methods
 - prEN 15347-2 Quality grades of sorted Polyethylene (PE) wastes and specific test methods
 - prEN 15347-1 General characterisation
 - FprEN 15344 Plastics - Recycled plastics - Characterization of Polyethylene (PE) recyclates
 - FprEN 18067 Plastics - Recycled plastics - Characterization of Acrylonitrile-Butadiene-Styrene (ABS) recyclates

- CEN/TC 261/SC 4/WG 10 - *Design for recycling for plastic packaging products*. CETEC is taking part in 15 projects for the development of PrEN-18120 Packaging - Design for recycling for plastic packaging products:
 - Part 1: Definitions and principles for design-for-recycling of plastic packaging
 - Part 2: Process and governance structure to evaluate the recyclability of plastic packaging
 - Part 3: Sorting evaluation process for plastic packaging
 - Part 4: Guideline and protocols for PET bottles
 - Part 5: Guideline and protocols for PET rigid packaging (except bottles)
 - Part 6: Guideline and protocols for PE and PP rigid packaging
 - Part 7: Guideline and protocols for PE and PP flexible packaging
 - Part 8: Guideline and protocols for PS and XPS packaging
 - Part 9: Guideline and protocols for EPS packaging
 - Part 10: Recyclability evaluation process for plastic packaging - protocols for PET bottles
 - Part 11: Recyclability evaluation process for plastic packaging – protocols for PET rigid packaging (except bottles)
 - Part 12: Recyclability evaluation process for plastic packaging – protocols for PE and PP rigid packaging
 - Part 13: Recyclability evaluation process for plastic packaging – protocols for PE and PP flexible packaging
 - Part 14: Recyclability evaluation process for plastic packaging – protocols for PS and XPS packaging

- Part 15: Recyclability evaluation process for plastic packaging - protocols for EPS packaging

CTN-UNE 53/SC 8 – *Plastic recycling*. CETEC and SOLPLAST have participated in the drafting of a new standard about recycling of polyethylene-aluminium films, which could include some of the aluminised products derived from the AGRO2CIRCULAR. Requirements are being established and methods of analysis for determining aluminium content are being validated.

4.3.2 Development of a new pre-standard via CEN workshop: publication of CEN Workshop Agreement CWA.

Apart from the contributions to standardization within specific technical committees, the development of standardized guidelines for the characterization of extracts for the recycling/upcycling of organic agrifood wastes was identified as a very useful opportunity to the transfer of the methodologies to the market, with the final aim of facilitating the valorisation of agrifood wastes. The guidelines would be based on the D2.4 “Evaluation of extracts” led by DMC, José Manuel de la Torre.

Specifically, the standardization via a **CEN workshop** was considered as the more suitable option for requiring more flexible procedures than other standardization routes, and because there is no specific technical committee for addressing this topic. The CEN workshop can also allow to publish a new pre-standard, **CWA (CEN workshop agreement)**, within the Agro2Circular project timeframe, that could then be transformed into EN standards.

CEN and CENELEC develop European Standards (EN) and other publications, including Technical Specifications (TS), Technical Reports (TR) and CEN Workshop Agreements (CWA). The European Standardization System makes a significant contribution to the European market, embedded in a global economy, and disseminates the knowledge incorporated in these publications through its network of CEN and CENELEC (national) Members.

A CWA (CEN Workshop Agreement) is a deliverable, which may take various forms such as text file or computer code, developed and agreed by the participants in a temporary working group (CEN/CENELEC Workshop). It is designed to meet an immediate need, can be quickly developed and can be used as fast track to future standardization activities. The stakeholder involvement is limited to those directly interested in the subject. The process for initiating and developing a CWA is illustrated in Figure 2. The green arrows in the Figure 2 indicate the opportunities of public participation in the process.

Figure 2 - Process for initiating and developing a CWA

It was decided to launch a CEN workshop titled 'Guidelines for characterization of extracts for the recycling/upcycling of organic agrifood wastes', where a document with the same title would be agreed by the workshop participants, to be published by CEN as CWA. The WS Chair is Jose Manuel de la Torre from DMC Research Centre, and the secretary is Ana Benedicto from UNE (Spanish Association for Standardization).

The process initiated with the submission of the proposal to CEN/CENELEC and with the development of the project plan (all details can be found in Annex 2 and 3, respectively). The initiation of the Agro2Circular CEN workshop was approved by CEN/CENELEC. The proposal and the project plan were opened for public commenting and participation in the workshop on 2024-03-11:

<https://www.cencenelec.eu/news-and-events/news/2024/workshop/2024-03-11-agro2circular/> (Figure 3).

The “proposal form” and the “project plan” (Annex 2 and 3, respectively) for CEN workshop development were prepared and submitted to CEN for approval. The initiation of the Agro2Circular CEN workshop was approved, and the initiative was announced in the CEN/CENELEC webpage:

Figure 3 -1 Screenshot of CEN workshop announcement online

The Kick of Meeting of the CEN workshop was held on April 5th, 2024 (screenshot of the online KoM in Figure 4). The first draft was presented by the workshop chair and project leader Jose Manuel de la Torre and discussed by the participants.

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Figure 42 - Screenshot of the online CEN WS KoM

Then, the draft was submitted to a commenting period (from 2024-04-17 to 2024-05-09). Once the feedbacks received were analyzed and the comments incorporated, the final version was submitted for the participants to confirm their endorsement to the CWA (the entities and people on behalf endorsing the document are listed in the forewords). The final version was submitted to CEN for publication in September 2024, effectively made available on 2024-10-09 [CEN](#).

The CWAs is available for free download from the CEN/CENELEC website: <https://www.cencenelec.eu/get-involved/research-and-innovation/horizon-europe-projects/cwa-download-area/>

The direct link for downloading is below:

[CWA 18149:2024](#) Guidelines for characterization of extracts for the recycling/upcycling of organic agrifood wastes (AGRO2CIRCULAR)

5. Conclusions

Following the Agro2Circular standardization strategy, different actions for contributing to standardization were made by the Agro2Circular project. The A2C research objectives, activities and expected outcomes were disseminated into the standardization network via communication with the relevant CEN technical committees: CEN/TC 444 Environmental characterization of solid matrices and CEN/TC 249 Plastics.

Subsequent interactions with the technical committees led to the A2C contribution to the development, drafting and revision of different standards in specific CEN working groups: CEN/TC 249/WG 7 - *Thermoplastic films for use in agriculture*, CEN/TC 249/WG 9 - *Bio-based and biodegradable plastics*, CEN/TC 249/WG 26 - *Agricultural Plastic products – Design for recycling, use, removal, collection and recycling*, CEN/TC 249/WG 11 - *Plastics recycling*, CEN/TC 261/SC 4/WG 10 - *Design for recycling for plastic packaging products*, and CTN-UNE 53/SC 8 – *Plastic recycling*.

A very relevant Agro2Circular contribution to standardization has been the development of the new European standard, CWA 18149:2024, titled: “Guidelines for characterization of extracts for the recycling/upcycling of organic agrifood wastes (AGRO2CIRCULAR)”. This document provides the basis to systematically compare results across extraction technologies and different raw materials and will allow the end-users of the extracts to evaluate their suitability for the specific final products.

The publication, through the CWA 18149:2024, of standardized methods and guidelines to characterize and evaluate the extracts will pave the way for valorising agrifood wastes by green routes to obtain bioactives for the production of nutraceuticals, functional foods, and cosmetics.

6. Annexes

Find below subsequently the annexes corresponding to:

6.1 A2C Dossier

6.2 A2C CEN workshop proposal form

6.3 A2C CEN workshop project plan

Agro2Circular

TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION
FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE
AGRIFOOD SECTOR

The hidden value of agrifood sector residues

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

Technical references

Project Acronym	Agro2Circular
Project Title	TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR
Project Coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó CETEC fuensanta.monzo@agro2circular.org
Project Duration	October 2021 – September 2024 (36 months)

Document history

V	Date	Comments
v0.1		First draft of document
v0.x		Revised version based on the comments of Name Reviewer(s) - Organisation
v1.0		First final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.
v1.1		First draft based upon first final version
v2.0		Second final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, (will be) submitted to EC.

Document Distribution Log

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v1.0	23/09/22	Alejandro Arribas, Fuensanta Monzó

Verification and approval

	Name	Date
Approval Final Dossier by coordinator	Fuensanta Monzó	23/09/22

Disclaimer and acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036838

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the views of the author(s) the European Research Executive Agency (REA) is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. Whilst efforts have been made to ensure the accuracy and completeness of this document, the A2C consortium shall not be liable for any errors or omissions, however caused.

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1 Summary

Agro2Circular (A2C) project is focused on the implementation of the first territorial systemic solution for the upcycling of most relevant residues in the agrifood sector (fruits & vegetables and plastic multilayers) into high added value products, powered by a digital tool and constructed upon a systemic approach with high replicable/scalable potential. Through this solution, A2C will face important industrial, economic & social challenges in the agrifood sector:

- The fruits & vegetables (F&V) are the group of major contribution to food waste along the food supply chain rising up to > 40% of waste, and are as excellent source of natural bioactives. However, these F&V wastes are not exploited. A2C will valorise them by green routes to obtain these bioactives for the production of nutraceuticals, functional foods, and cosmetics.
- Multilayer plastic films are widely used as industrial packaging for the protection of food and agriculture for crops due to their unique barrier properties. However, there is a lack of sorting and recycling technologies for an economic and environmentally sustainable valorisation of these multilayer structures. A2C will develop the first recycling value chain for post-industrial multilayer films based on a synergistic approach combining innovative sorting, physical delamination, enzymatic depolymerisation, decontamination & mechanical recycling.
- There is a lack of digitalisation in the agrifood sector. A2C will implement a Data Integration System (DIS) as a digital tool for ensuring traceability and as Predictive Decision Tool in the agrifood sector.

A2C will be a demonstrated in the Región de Murcia (Spain) and replicable systemic solution throughout Europe for the territorial deployment of the circular economy.

2 Agro2Circular description

2.1 Agro2Circular value chain

Figure 1: A2C value chain

Agro2circular project involves the agri-food sector, the technologies for the recycling of the organic agri-food wastes and the technologies for the sorting and recycling of multilayer plastic residues. These agri-food wastes and multilayer plastic residues will be upcycling into new cosmetics, nutraceuticals, food formulation, recyclable barrier agricultural films and cecyclable food barrier packaging. A Data Integration System (DIS) will assure the trazability, security and the strategic decision aid tool.

2.2 Agri-food industry food waste

Figure 2: Agrifood industry food waste

From agri-food wastes, and different extraction techniques, high value product will be extracted and use to manufacture new food formualtions, new nutraceuticals formulatiois and new cosmetic formulations. The organic residues will be use to produce bioplastic (PHBV).

2.3 Agri-food industry plastic waste

Aseptic bag-in-box
Multilayer multimaterial structures
!No recycling solution available!

Figure 3: Aseptic bag-in-box residue

Aseptic bag-in-box residues from agri-food industries still has no recycling solution.

2.4 Multilayer aseptic bags upcycling

Figure 4: Multilayer aseptic bags upcycling

Aseptic bag-in-box will be upcycling through a complex recycling system to produce again barrier food packaging and biodegradable food packaging.

2.5 Agri-food industry plastic waste

Multilayer gas barrier film for soil disinfection

!No recycling solution available!

Figure 5: Agri-food industry plastic waste

Multilayer gas barrier film for soil disinfection still has no recycling solution.

2.6 Multilayer soil disinfection films

Figure 6: Multilayer soil disinfection films

The multilayer soil disinfection films will be upcycling to high barrier plastic films.

2.7 Agro2Circular data integration system

Figure 7: Agro2Circular data integration system

A data integration system will be use as a traceability tool and as a predictive tool in order to control all the integrated processes.

2.8 Systemic approach

Figure 8: Systemic approach

The A2C project will involve all project actors with as many members of society as possible.

LOCAL DISSEMINATION, CITIZENS' AWARENESS & TRAINING

- Food waste upcycling in weekly local street markets
- Documentary made by students
- Videogame made by students

Figure 9: Project management

Besides the project management, great importance has been given to local dissemination, awareness raising and training of citizens with actions involving local students.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101036838.

Figure 10: Areas of project involvement

The project will assess the environmental and circularity requirements. A2C also will analyse the social and economic impact. The project try to follow the European standards and identify the possible lack of standards in fields like environmental characterization of solid matrices, plastics recycling, thermoplastic films for use in agriculture, utensils in contact with food and biodegradable plastics. Finally, A2C will spread the results to the society.

2.9 Scalability & replicability

Figure 11: Scalability and replicability

The territorial solution will be scaled, and also it will be replicated in Italia and Lithuanian.

2.10 Expected Impact

Figure 12: Expected impact

**Proposal for a CEN Workshop
on "Guidelines for
characterization of extracts for
the recycling/upcycling of
organic agrifood wastes"**

1 Proposal Form for the Workshop proposer

Details of the Workshop proposer:

Name: José Manuel de la Torre Ramírez
Organization: AGRO2CIRCULAR Project (European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101036838)
Postal address: Camino de Jayena, 82. 18620. Alhendín (Granada). Spain.
Email: josemanuel.delatorre@dmcrc.com
Phone: +34655779320
Webpage: <https://www.domca.com/>

Already known partners:

DMC RESEARCH CENTER SL
CENTRO TÉCNOLÓGICO DEL CALZADO Y DEL PLÁSTICO
CENTRO TECNOLÓGICO NACIONAL DE LA CONSERVA
AGROTRANSFORMADOS S.A.
LABORATORIOS ALMOND S.L.
PROEXPORT-ASSOCIATION OF PRODUCERS AND EXPORTERS FROM REGION OF MURCIA
CITROMIL SL
SAIREM
EXPERIMENTAL STATION FOR THE FOOD PRESERVATION INDUSTRY
FUNDACIÓN CLUSTER AGROALIMENTARIO DE LA REGION DE MURCIA
FUNDACIÓN PRIMAFRÍO
CETEC BIOTECHNOLOGY SL

Title of the proposed Workshop:

Guidelines for characterization of extracts for the recycling/upcycling of organic agrifood wastes

Background/Objectives:

- Motivation for the creation of this Workshop

This workshop is motivated by the currently ongoing Horizon 2020 AGRO2CIRCULAR project (TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR), whose general objective is the implementation of the first territorial systemic solution for the upcycling of most relevant residues in the agrifood sector (fruits&vegetables and plastic multilayers) into high added value products, powered by a digital tool and constructed upon a systemic approach with high replicable/scalable potential. Specifically, the fruits & vegetables are the group of major contribution to food waste along the food supply chain rising up to > 40% of waste, and are as excellent source of natural bioactives. However, these fruits & vegetables wastes are not exploited. Agro2Circular project works for valorising them by green routes to obtain these bioactives for the production of nutraceuticals, functional foods, and cosmetics.

The creation of this CEN Workshop was identified by the project consortium as a very useful way for the translation of its results to marketable solutions. This initiative aligns the Agro2Circular project with Commission Recommendation (EU) 2023/498 “Code of Practice on standardisation in the European Research Area” and Council Recommendation (EU) 2022/2415 “Guiding principles for knowledge valorisation”.

This workshop will be used for the dissemination of the project and its results reaching stakeholders on national, European and international level. Agro2Circular will lead the development of a CWA closely connected to project objectives and the developed technologies and processes in order to bring these closer to the market and to spread technological advances.

- Market environment

The European Commission's policy advocates increasing the recovery of organic waste, reducing the volume of by-products that end up in landfills or incineration, with the consequent reduction of greenhouse gas emissions.

Enhancing the recovery of organic by-products is also in line with EU policies of green transition and circular economy.

A wide array of studies has demonstrated the potential of different extracts from agri-food wastes for the enrichment of food formulations as natural alternatives to synthetic additives.

Conventional synthetic food additives	Alternative natural extracts	Wastes
Thickening, texturizing, gelling, & stabilizing agents- Hydrocolloids, phosphates	Dietary fiber, pectin, agar	Fruit (olive, grape, pineapple, citrus, apple, pear), vegetable, algae
Colorants- Erythrosine (red), cantaxanthin (orange), amaranth (azoic red), tartrazine (azoic yellow), and annatto bixine (yellow orange)	Carotenoids: β -carotene, astaxanthin, canthaxanthin, zeaxanthin.	Tomato, paprika, and algae, berries, citrus peels
Emulsifiers- polysaccharides (gum arabic), phospholipids (lecithins)	Okara protein	Soy
Antioxidants- Butylated hydroxy anisole, butylated hydroxytoluene, ethoxyquin, tert-butylhydroquinone, propyl gallate	Phenolic substances	Fruits, vegetables
Preservatives- Nitrates (E240-E259) and nitrites (E249-E250)	Enzymes, bacteriocins, fungicides, salts, essential oils	Fruit peels and seeds

Furthermore, natural compounds may also be regarded as nutraceutical ingredients for products with enhanced nutritional value, health benefits, and longer shelf-life, highlighting phenolics compounds and carotenoids (high antioxidant potential), and dietary fibers (digestive properties). Moreover, some agrifood wastes extracts have been demonstrated for their cosmetic activity (carotenoids from pineapple) or already employed in cosmetic formulations (such as commercially available lycopene from tomato extraction or essential oils from citrus). But many others could be proposed for further applications, where less effective & more expensive products are currently being used.

Organic solvent extraction is the conventional method to recover bioactives from vegetal matrix including agrifood wastes, however it has important problems: low selective yield (many other molecules co-extracted with the target ones), environmental unsustainability. To overcome the problems alternative green extraction processes are emerging.

The suitability of the extracts obtained from the agrifood wastes to be valorised into different products depends on the raw material and the extraction routes of the bioactive compounds. However, standardized methods or guidelines to characterize and evaluate the extracts do not exist so far. The development of these guidelines will facilitate to systematically compare results across extraction technologies and different raw materials and will allow the end-users of the extracts to evaluate their suitability for the specific final products. This CEN workshop can strongly support the transfer to the market of the new technologies and methods implemented by the Agro2Circular for the valorization of the agrifood wastes.

Scope of the proposed Workshop (planned area of application):

The planned document specifies the methodologies for the analysis of aqueous natural antioxidant extracts obtained from wastes and by-products of the agri-food industry. These methodologies encompass the determination of total polyphenols content, total flavonoid content and antioxidant activity assessment through colorimetric assays employing various techniques. The method for quantifying total polyphenol content involves the use of the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, while the total flavonoid content is determined using the aluminium chloride method. Multiple methods for evaluating antioxidant activity are described, including ABTS, DPPH, and FRAP assays.

The planned document is applicable to aqueous extracts obtained from agri-food waste and by-products, specifically those originating from vegetables and fruits. Depending on the specific matrix and composition of the extract, it may be necessary to employ different methods for characterizing these extracts.

Are the following aspects potentially affected?

	YES	NO
Safety matters	<input type="checkbox"/> ¹	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Management system aspects	<input type="checkbox"/> ²	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

¹ For CEN: The CEN/CENELEC Workshop proposal shall be submitted to CEN/BT for decision. For CENELEC: Work on the proposed CEN/CENELEC Workshop shall not be initiated.

² The CEN/CENELEC Workshop proposal shall be submitted to the CEN/CENELEC BT(s) for decision.

Conformity assessment aspects	<input type="checkbox"/> ³	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Security matters	<input type="checkbox"/> ⁴	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

<Add information/explanations to the points marked yes">

Theme related standardization Technical Bodies, standards or regulations, if applicable:

The subjects of the planned CWA are not at present the subject of a standard. There are also no committees, standards and/or other technical specifications that deal with related subjects.

Optional attachments:

<List optional information, e.g. estimated project duration and date of the Kick-off, manuscript, short description, presentation, etc.>

³ CEN/CENELEC Internal Regulations - Part 3, 33 applies.

⁴ For projects dealing with security matters the security risk analysis provided below (item 3) shall be carried out.

2 Proposal Form for the Workshop secretariat

CEN Workshop on "Guidelines for characterization of extracts for the recycling/upcycling of organic agrifood wastes"

Details of the Workshop secretary:

Name: Ana Benedicto
Organization: UNE Asociación Española de Normalización
Postal address: C/Génova 13, 28004 Madrid (SPAIN)
Email: abenedicto@une.org
Phone: +34 650 50 02 08
Webpage: une.org

Finance:

The administrative costs of the CEN Workshop will be financed by resources from the Agro2Circular project. The final document will include the following paragraph: "Results incorporated in this CEN Workshop Agreement have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101036838".

Both registration and participation at the CEN Workshop described here are free of charge. The use of electronic meetings will be preferred. Nevertheless, in the case of physical meetings, they will be held in Europe and each participant has to bear his/her own costs for travel, accommodation, and subsistence.

According to CEN/CENELEC Guide 29, the resulting CWA will be available for free downloading from CEN-CENELEC Webpage, since it is under R&D domain. Related cost will also be covered by Agro2Circular project.

Drafting and Dissemination:

The preliminary Workshop schedule will be the following:

	Activities	Schedule
1	WS kick-off meeting + presentation of first draft of the CWA	2024-04
2	Elaboration and agreement on the draft CWA (3 virtual meetings are envisaged)	2024-04 / 2024-08
5	Publication of CWA after editorial check by CCMC	2024-09

In relation with dissemination, as indicated above, the CWA will be available for free download from CEN-CENELEC webpage (CWA download area).

The results obtained from this workshop will be disseminated throughout the specific Agro2Circular website (<https://agro2circular.eu/>) and social media (Twitter and LinkedIn), and into the Agro2Circular dissemination network, including the selected stakeholders and multipliers, such as the scientific community, technical experts, strategic experts and policy makers and the general public and end-users. This will be done according to the Agro2Circular dissemination strategic plan.

Does the proposed CWA conflict with an EN or an HD?

	YES	NO
EN	<input type="checkbox"/> ⁵	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
HD (CENELEC)	<input type="checkbox"/> ⁵	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Is the proposed CWA within the domain of an existing CEN and/or CENELEC Technical Body?

No

CEN/CENELEC Management Centre (to be completed by CCMC):

Name of the CCMC project manager:

Organization: CCMC

Postal address: Rue de la Science 23, 1040 Brussels

Email:

Phone: +32 2 550 xxxx

Webpage: <https://www.cencenelec.eu/aboutus/MgtCentre/Pages/default.aspx>

Response of identified potentially affected CEN/CENELEC TCs

	YES	NO
Is there an active work item covering the scope of the planned CWA?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Are there arguments against the topic of the planned CWA?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<Add information/explanations to the points marked „yes“>		

⁵ Work on the proposed CWA shall not be initiated.

3 Security risk analysis

3.1 General

Security risk analysis is a process of identifying and analysing the main negative factors that may affect a standardization project's objectives. The following is targeted at secretariats of CEN/CENELEC Workshop Agreements (CWA) dealing with security issues. Its purpose is to help them identify and mitigate the risks associated with their project. It is structured around two main security threats that can affect the success of the work: major diverging interests among stakeholders and sensitive information.

3.2 Risk analysis on major diverging interest among stakeholders

Diverging interests among stakeholders can impede the process in reaching agreement on the CWA and even lead to failure to deliver the planned CWA. In order to identify and possibly mitigate the risks, the following questions should be reviewed:

- Is the planned CWA expected to have a major impact on the security policy/strategy of the core stakeholders?
- Does the scope of the CWA cover products or services with a clear dual-use purpose (i.e. which can be used for military purposes)?

3.3 Risk analysis on sensitive information

- In light of the scope of the CWA, is it likely that it may deal with sensitive information? If so, what is the information sensitivity level?
- Is there a need for a (non-)disclosure agreement?
- Is there any conflict of interest for stakeholders involved in the CEN/CENELEC Workshop, regarding especially the use they may make of any information they receive during the development of the CWA?
- What steps should be taken to manage information dissemination and storage (e.g. memory stick, emailing, storage) during the development process of the CWA?

The planned CWA is **not** expected to have a major impact on the security policy/strategy of the core stakeholders here.

The scope of the CWA does **not** cover products or services with a clear dual-use purpose (i.e. which can be used for military purposes).

In light of the scope of the CWA, it **is not** likely that it may deal with sensitive information.

There is **no** need for a (non-)disclosure agreement.

There is **no** conflict of interest for stakeholders involved in the CEN/CENELEC Workshop, regarding especially the use they may make of any information they receive during the development of the CWA.

The information will be disseminated throughout emailing, including the corresponding disclaimer to guarantee the confidentiality of the information contained in the messages, and the protection of personal data. Each participant will choose its own suitable storage form that likewise guarantee the indicated above. All communication shall be copied to Secretariat and all participants to ensure transparency, openness and equal treatment of all stakeholders.

**Draft Project plan for the CEN
Workshop on "Guidelines for
characterization of extracts for
the recycling/upcycling of
organic agrifood wastes"**

**Requests to participate in the Workshop
and/or comments on the project plan are
to be submitted by 2024-04-01 to
abenedicto@une.org¹**

Recipients of this project plan are kindly requested to name all patent rights known to them to be relevant to the Workshop and to make available all supporting documents.

2024-02-26 (Version 1)

¹ Applications for participating in the Workshop and comments on the project plan that are not received by the deadline do not need to be taken into consideration. Once constituted, the Workshop will decide whether or not to consider the comments received in good time.

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Summary

This CEN workshop is a proposal coming from the research H2020 project AGRO2CIRCULAR (full title: TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR), with the aim of transferring the developed technologies and processes to marketable solutions and of spreading the technological advances. A document is expected to be agreed, regarding the characterization and evaluation of extracts for the recycling/upcycling of organic agrifood wastes.

1 Status of the project plan

Draft project plan for public commenting (Version 1)

This draft project plan is intended to inform the public of a new Workshop. Any interested party can take part in this Workshop and/or comment on this draft project plan. Please send any requests to participate or comments by e-mail to abenedicto@une.org.

All those who have applied for participation or have commented on the project plan by the deadline will be invited to the kick-off meeting of the Workshop on **2024-04-05**.

2 Workshop proposer and Workshop participants

2.1 Workshop proposer

<u>Person or organisation</u>	<u>Short description and interest in the subject</u>
<u>Agro2Circular Project Consortium</u>	<p>This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101036838.</p> <p>Agro2Circular is EU project boosting the upcycling of agri-food wastes through innovative routes of valorisation, leading to high extraction yields, bioactives with the purity and stability required to be used for the production of new food, cosmetic and nutraceutical formulation.</p>

2.2 Other potential participants

This CWA will be developed in a Workshop (temporary body) that is open to any interested party. The participation of other experts would be helpful and is desired. It is recommended that:

- Industry and commerce, agricultural primary production sector and food processing sector, cosmetics and nutraceuticals producers.
- Government, regulatory bodies on agri-food sector and cosmetic and nutraceutical sector.
- Consumers
- Academic and research, experts on extraction technologies and on new food, nutraceuticals & cosmetic formulations.

take part in the development of this CWA.

2.3 Participants at the kick-off meeting

The following organisations already signed up to the kick-off meeting prior to the publication of the draft project plan.

DMC RESEARCH CENTER SL
CENTRO TÉCNOLÓGICO DEL CALZADO Y DEL PLÁSTICO

CENTRO TECNOLÓGICO NACIONAL DE LA CONSERVA
AGROTRANSFORMADOS S.A.
LABORATORIOS ALMOND S.L.
PROEXPORT-ASSOCIATION OF PRODUCERS AND EXPORTERS FROM REGION OF MURCIA
CITROMIL SL
SAIREM
EXPERIMENTAL STATION FOR THE FOOD PRESERVATION INDUSTRY
FUNDACIÓN CLUSTER AGROALIMENTARIO DE LA REGION DE MURCIA
FUNDACIÓN PRIMAFRÍO
CETEC BIOTECHNOLOGY SL

3 Workshop objectives and scope

3.1 Background

- **Motivation for the creation of this Workshop**

This workshop is motivated by the currently ongoing Horizon 2020 AGRO2CIRCULAR project (TERRITORIAL CIRCULAR SYSTEMIC SOLUTION FOR THE UPCYCLING OF RESIDUES FROM THE AGRIFOOD SECTOR), whose general objective is the implementation of the first territorial systemic solution for the upcycling of most relevant residues in the agrifood sector (fruits&vegetables and plastic multilayers) into high added value products, powered by a digital tool and constructed upon a systemic approach with high replicable/scalable potential. Specifically, the fruits & vegetables are the group of major contribution to food waste along the food supply chain rising up to > 40% of waste, and are as excellent source of natural bioactives. However, these fruits & vegetables wastes are not exploited. Agro2Circular project works for valorising them by green routes to obtain these bioactives for the production of nutraceuticals, functional foods, and cosmetics.

The creation of this CEN Workshop was identified by the project consortium as a very useful way for the translation of its results to marketable solutions. This initiative aligns the Agro2Circular project with Commission Recommendation (EU) 2023/498 “Code of Practice on standardisation in the European Research Area” and Council Recommendation (EU) 2022/2415 “Guiding principles for knowledge valorisation”.

This workshop will be used for the dissemination of the project and its results reaching stakeholders on national, European and international level. Agro2Circular will lead the development of a CWA closely connected to project objectives and the developed technologies and processes in order to bring these closer to the market and to spread technological advances.

- **Market environment**

The European Commission's policy advocates increasing the recovery of organic waste, reducing the volume of by-products that end up in landfills or incineration, with the consequent reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. Enhancing the recovery of organic by-products is also in line with EU policies of green transition and circular economy.

A wide array of studies has demonstrated the potential of different extracts from agri-food wastes for the enrichment of food formulations as natural alternatives to synthetic additives.

Conventional synthetic food additives	Alternative natural extracts	Wastes
Thickening, texturizing, gelling, & stabilizing agents- Hydrocolloids, phosphates	Dietary fiber, pectin, agar	Fruit (olive, grape, pineapple, citrus, apple, pear), vegetable, algae
Colorants- Erythrosine (red), cantaxanthin (orange), amaranth (azoic red), tartrazine (azoic yellow), and annatto bixine (yellow orange)	Carotenoids: β -carotene, astaxanthin, canthaxanthin, zeaxanthin.	Tomato, paprika, and algae, berries, citrus peels
Emulsifiers- polysaccharides (gum arabic), phospholipids (lecithins)	Okara protein	Soy
Antioxidants- Butylated hydroxy anisole, butylated hydroxytoluene, ethoxyquin, tert-butylhydroquinone, propyl gallate	Phenolic substances	Fruits, vegetables
Preservatives- Nitrates (E240-E259) and nitrites (E249-E250)	Enzymes, bacteriocins, fungicides, salts, essential oils	Fruit peels and seeds

Furthermore, natural compounds may also be regarded as nutraceutical ingredients for products with enhanced nutritional value, health benefits, and longer shelf-life, highlighting phenolics compounds and carotenoids (high antioxidant potential), and dietary fibers (digestive properties). Moreover, some agrifood wastes extracts have been demonstrated for their cosmetic activity (carotenoids from pineapple) or already employed in cosmetic

formulations (such as commercially available lycopene from tomato extraction or essential oils from citrus). But many others could be proposed for further applications, where less effective & more expensive products are currently being used.

Organic solvent extraction is the conventional method to recover bioactives from vegetal matrix including agrifood wastes, however it has important problems: low selective yield (many other molecules co-extracted with the target ones), environmental unsustainability. To overcome the problems alternative green extraction processes are emerging.

The suitability of the extracts obtained from the agrifood wastes to be valorised into different products depends on the raw material and the extraction routes of the bioactive compounds. However, standardized methods or guidelines to characterize and evaluate the extracts do not exist so far. The development of these guidelines will facilitate to systematically compare results across extraction technologies and different raw materials and will allow the end-users of the extracts to evaluate their suitability for the specific final products. This CEN workshop can strongly support the transfer to the market of the new technologies and methods implemented by the Agro2Circular for the valorization of the agrifood wastes.

3.2 Scope

The planned document specifies the methodologies for the analysis of aqueous natural antioxidant extracts obtained from wastes and by-products of the agri-food industry. These methodologies encompass the determination of total polyphenols content, total flavonoid content and antioxidant activity assessment through colorimetric assays employing various techniques. The method for quantifying total polyphenol content involves the use of the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, while the total flavonoid content is determined using the aluminum chloride method. Multiple methods for evaluating antioxidant activity are described, including ABTS, DPPH, and FRAP assays.

The planned document is applicable to aqueous extracts obtained from agri-food waste and by-products, specifically those originating from vegetables and fruits. Depending on the specific matrix and composition of the extract, it may be necessary to employ different methods for characterizing these extracts.

3.3 Related activities

The subjects of the planned CWA are not at present the subject of a standard. There are also no committees, standards and/or other technical specifications that deal with related subjects.

4 Workshop programme

4.1 General

The kick-off meeting is planned to take place on 5th April 2024 on-line.

A total of 4 virtual workshop meetings (kick-off meeting and Workshop meetings) will be held, during which the content of the CWAs will be presented, discussed and approved.

The CWA will be drawn up in English (language of meetings, minutes, etc.). The CWA will be written in English.

4.2 Workshop schedule

Table 1 shows the preliminary timescale and work programme for the workshop, which may be modified according to the progress of the project.

Table 1: Workshop schedule (preliminary)

CEN Workshop	JAN23	FEB23	MAR24	APR24	MAY24	JUN24	JUL24	AGO24	SEP24	OCT24
Initiation										
1. Proposal form submission and TC response										
2. Project plan development										
3. Open commenting period on draft project plan (mandatory)										
Operation										
4. Kick-off meeting										
5. CWA(s) development										
6. CWA(s) finalised and approved by Workshop participants										
Publication										
7. CWA(s) publication										
Dissemination (see 7)										
Milestones				K	V	V		V/A	P	D

- K** Kick-off
- V** Virtual Workshop meeting
- A** Adoption of CWA
- P** Publication of CWA
- D** Online distribution of CWA

5 Resource planning

The administrative costs of the CEN Workshop will be financed by resources from the Agro2Circular project. The final document will include the following paragraph: "Results incorporated in this CEN Workshop Agreement have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101036838".

Both registration and participation at the CEN Workshop described here are free of charge. The use of electronic meetings will be preferred. Nevertheless, in the case of physical meetings, they will be held in Europe and each participant has to bear his/her own costs for travel, accommodation, and subsistence.

6 Workshop structure and rules of cooperation

6.1 Participation in the Workshop

The Workshop will be constituted during the course of the kick-off meeting. By approving this project plan, the interested parties declare their willingness to participate in the Workshop and will be formally named as Workshop participants, with the associated rights and duties. Participants at the kick-off meeting who do not approve the project plan are not given the status of a Workshop participant and are thus excluded from further decisions made during the kick-off meeting and from any other decisions regarding the Workshop.

As a rule, the request to participate in the Workshop is closed once it is constituted. The current Workshop participants shall decide whether any additional members will be accepted or not.

Any new participant in the Workshop at a later date is decided on by the participants making up the Workshop at that time. It is particularly important to consider these aspects:

- a. expansion would be conducive to shortening the duration of the Workshop or to avoiding or averting an impending delay in the planned duration of the Workshop;
- b. the expansion would not result in the Workshop taking longer to complete;
- c. the new Workshop participant would not address any new or complementary issues beyond the scope defined and approved in the project plan;
- d. the new Workshop participant would bring complementary expertise into the Workshop in order to incorporate the latest scientific findings and state-of-the-art knowledge;
- e. the new Workshop participant would actively participate in the drafting of the manuscript by submitting concrete, not abstract, proposals and contributions;
- f. the new Workshop participant would ensure wider application of the CWA.

All Workshop participants who voted for the publication of the CWA or its draft will be named as authors in the European Foreword, including the organisations which they represent. All Workshop participants who voted against the publication of the CWA, or who have abstained, will not be named in the European Foreword.

6.2 Workshop responsibilities

The Workshop Chair is responsible for content management and any decision-making and voting procedures. The Workshop Chair is supported by the Workshop Vice-Chair and the responsible Workshop secretariat, whereby the Workshop secretariat will always remain neutral regarding the content of the CWA. Furthermore, the Workshop secretariat shall ensure that CEN-CENELEC's rules of procedure, rules of presentation, and the principles governing the publication of CWA have been observed. Should a Workshop Chair no longer be able to carry out her/his duties, the Workshop secretariat shall initiate the election of a new Workshop Chair. The list below covers the main tasks of the Workshop Chair. It is not intended to be exhaustive.

- Content related contact point for the Workshop
- Presides at Workshop meetings
- Ensures that the development of the CWA respects the principles and content of the adopted project plan
- Manages the consensus building process, decides when the Workshop participants have reached agreement on the final CWA, on the basis of the comments received
- Ensures due information exchange with the Workshop secretariat
- Represents the Workshop and its results to exterior

The Workshop secretariat, provided by a CEN/CENELEC national member, is responsible for organising and leading the kick-off meeting, in consultation with the Workshop proposer. Further Workshop meetings and/or web

conferences shall be organised by the Workshop secretariat in consultation with the Workshop Chair. The list below covers the main tasks of the Workshop secretariat. It is not intended to be exhaustive.

- Administrative and organisational contact point for the Workshop
- Ensures that the development of the CWA respects the principles and content of the adopted project plan and of the requirements of the CEN-CENELEC Guide 29
- Formally registers Workshop participants and maintains record of participating organisations and individuals
- Offers infrastructure and manage documents and their distribution through an electronic platform
- Prepares agenda and distribute information on meetings and meeting minutes as well as follow-up actions of the Workshop
- Initiates and manage CWA approval process upon decision by the Workshop Chair
- Interface with CEN-CENELEC Management Centre (CCMC) and Workshop Chair regarding strategic directions, problems arising, and external relationships
- Advises on CEN-CENELEC rules and bring any major problems encountered (if any) in the development of the CWA to the attention of CEN-CENELEC Management Centre (CCMC)
- Administrates the connection with relevant CEN or CENELEC/TCs

6.3 Decision making process

Each Workshop participant is entitled to vote and has one vote. If an organisation sends several experts to the Workshop, that organisation has only one vote, regardless of how many Workshop participants it sends. Transferring voting rights to other Workshop participants is not permitted. During voting procedures, decisions are passed by simple majority; abstentions do not count.

If Workshop participants cannot be present in the meetings when the CWA or its draft is adopted, an alternative means of including them in the voting procedure shall be used.

7 Dissemination and participation strategy

Proposal form submission

The Workshop proposal will be disseminated to the following relevant stakeholders and bodies for their information:

- CEN/TC 444 Environmental characterization of solid matrices
- CEN/TC 392 Cosmetics
- CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods

Open commenting period on draft project plan

The project plan will be disseminated to the following relevant stakeholders and bodies for commenting:

- CEN/TC 444 Environmental characterization of solid matrices
- CEN/TC 392 Cosmetics
- CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods

In addition to the CCMC website, the project plan and the date of the kick-off meeting will be advertised on the Agro2Circular project webpage (<https://agro2circular.eu/>) and its social networks to raise awareness. Interested parties are requested to contribute either through commenting of the project plan (short term) or through Workshop participation (long term).

CWA publication

The final CWA will be disseminated to the following relevant stakeholders and bodies:

- CEN/TC 444 Environmental characterization of solid matrices
- CEN/TC 392 Cosmetics
- CEN/TC 275 Food analysis - Horizontal methods

In addition to the CCMC website, the final CWA will be advertised on:

- Agro2Circular project webpage (<https://agro2circular.eu/>)
- Agro2Circular social media:
 - Facebook
 - Instagram
 - LinkedIn
 - Twitter
- Research Gate

8 Contacts

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